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Development of a numerical model of CaCl_2 hydration and dehydration reaction for thermochemical energy storage

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Abstract. Periodical variations experienced by buildings' energy demand and supply might be tackled by means of Thermal Energy Storage (TES) systems. Among these, thermochemical heat storage (TCHS) by means of thermochemical material (TCM) is one of the most promising, allowing the greatest energy storage density per unit volume, negligible heat losses and long-term storage. As part of the Horizon Europe project "ECHO", a preliminary 2D model of the TCHS system was developed with the software COMSOL Multiphysics as a tool to support the real-scale prototype design, anticipating the behaviour of the system, as well as the implementation of the control algorithm. The model was implemented to work in both charge (dehydration) and discharge (hydration) without having to change the reaction kinetics equation from time to time, only based on the instant-by-instant boundary conditions. This ability to switch from hydration to dehydration and vice versa at any time makes it possible to estimate the performance of the TCM even in the event of not being completely hydrated or dehydrated, and also to establish some relationship between the TCM charging and discharging times.

1. Introduction

The greatest energy-consumer sector is the building and construction one [1], accounting for about 75% of primary energy supply still based on fossil fuels [2], more than 30% of the consumptions on a global scale and almost 40% of the total energy-related CO_2 emissions [3]. This energy demand, however, experiences periodical variations and the same applies to energy supply, especially in case of renewable sources, whose fluctuations occur from daily to seasonal scales. Demand and supply are hardly synchronized and this non-correspondence can prevent the full exploitation of energy from renewable sources.

Thermal Energy Storage (TES) is among the most promising technologies to increase the efficiency of renewable energy sources [4]. TES, in fact, allows thermal energy to be stored by heating or cooling a medium so that the stored energy is available at a delayed time, thus overcoming the mismatch between energy supply and demand. In general, TES systems involve three steps, namely thermal charging, thermal storing and thermal discharging [5], and can be done in three ways, namely sensible heat storage (SHS), latent heat storage (LHS) and thermo-chemical storage (TCHS). Among these, TCHS emerges due to the higher energy storage density [6], smaller volume required [7] and negligible heat losses during storage [8] due to the conversion between chemical potential and heat energy.

Nomenclature list

$\alpha(t)$	reaction advancement factor, -
$\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t}$	reaction kinetics, s^{-1}
C_0	initial vapor concentration inside TCM, mol/m^3
C_f	final vapor concentration inside TCM, mol/m^3
$C_{(t)}$	vapor concentration inside TCM at time t, mol/m^3
c_s	salt specific heat, $\text{J}/(\text{kg}\cdot\text{K})$
c_v	vapor specific heat, $\text{J}/(\text{kg}\cdot\text{K})$
D_g	water vapor diffusion coefficient, m^2/s
ε	salt bed porosity, -
ΔH	reaction enthalpy, J/mol
λ_s	salt thermal conductivity, $\text{W}/(\text{m}\cdot\text{K})$
M_s	salt molecular mass, g/mol
M_v	vapor molecular mass, g/mol
p_{eq}	equilibrium pressure, Pa
p_{ref}	reference pressure, Pa
p_v	vapor pressure, Pa
ρ_s	salt density, kg/m^3
ρ_v	vapor density, kg/m^3
\dot{q}	volumetric heat source, W/m^3
R	universal gas constant, $\text{J}/(\text{mol}\cdot\text{K})$
ΔS	reaction entropy, $\text{J}/(\text{mol}\cdot\text{K})$
S_w	mass source of water vapor, $\text{kg}/(\text{m}^3\cdot\text{s})$
z	stoichiometric number, -

In a thermo-chemical system, a reactant ($A \cdot xB$) absorbs heat and then decomposes into two products (A and B) in the so-called charging phase, during which the absorbed heat is converted in stable chemical potential energy, which is then stored. The reversed reaction, renamed discharging phase, allows the recombination of A and B and the conversion of the chemical potential energy back into thermal energy. This reversible reaction is described as:

TCHS can be done by means of the so-called thermochemical materials (TCMs), such as salt hydrates like magnesium chloride ($\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) [9], calcium chloride ($\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) [10], strontium bromide ($\text{SrBr}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) [11] or magnesium sulphate ($\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$) [12] which are widely used due to their low cost, non-toxicity and regeneration temperature below 150°C .

Among these, CaCl_2 emerges as one of the most promising, due to its accessibility, cost-effectiveness, chemical stability, non-toxicity but most importantly its exceptional water adsorption capacity and energy storage potential. For these reasons, CaCl_2 is considered to be highly suitable in case of TES applications in buildings.

Depending on the boundary conditions in terms of temperature and vapor pressure, hydration and dehydration of CaCl_2 occurs in multiple steps. Each of these steps can be expressed through the general reactions:

However, pure salt hydrates are characterised by poor heat and mass transfer properties, which cause the relatively low thermal efficiency of the TCES system. Moreover, agglomerate and swelling of pure salt hydrates due to excessive absorption of water result in poor system cycle stability [13]. To solve these problems, researchers have developed the so-called SIM (*salt in matrix*), made of salt hydrates embedded in porous adsorbent materials, e.g., zeolites [14], expanded vermiculite [15] or expanded graphite [16]. The porous structure and the high thermal conductivity of the host matrix can effectively improve heat and mass transfer performance of TCMs, avoiding at the same time agglomeration and expansion, thus enhancing the system thermal efficiency and cycle stability [17]. On one side, the addition of inert materials can greatly extend the number of cycles of the salt, but on the other side, since the matrix is not involved in the adsorption and desorption process, the overall energy density of SIM is generally lower than that of pure salt.

The above-mentioned challenges can be addressed not just at material scale, but also at reactor scale. A reactor, in fact, should be carefully designed to facilitate heat and mass transfer and maximise the energy density while preventing the corrosion of the components and the agglomeration of the material. Moulakhnif et al. [18] classified TCM reactors into three main categories, namely packed bed reactors, modular reactors and moving bed reactors.

Packed bed reactors are the most used due to their simplicity, relatively low cost and easy maintenance. Researchers have focused on packed bed with the aim of minimizing heat losses and enhancing heat and mass transfer. For instance, in [19] a packed bed reactor was designed at lab scale using zeolite and cement composites along with strontium chloride, being able to enhance the power output and the temperature lift, reaching energy densities of 108-138 kWh/m³. In [20] a packed bed reactor using magnesium chloride was designed, concluding that decreasing the reactor area ratio the charging time can be reduced but the pressure drop is increased. In [21] a metal mesh-packed reactor was used, obtaining an increase of the thermal efficiency and of the energy storage density. Modular reactors are studied because of their flexibility which allows the enhancement heat and mass transfer. In [22] a modular packed bed reactor with 8 layers was built using strontium bromide as salt, investigating heat and mass transfer changes based on different boundary conditions. Results showed the permeability of the reactive bed changing with the density changing. In [23] an open sorption pipe using calcium chloride embedded in vermiculite was designed, concluding that increasing the input absolute humidity could lead to an increase of the power output, but experiencing heat losses to the environment. In [24] a packed bed reactor was designed made of two reactors that could be used both in series as well as in parallel, obtaining interesting results in terms of power output and material energy density. In moving bed reactors, where the TCM is continuously moving, heat transfer inside the bed is enhanced and more uniform temperatures can be obtained. In [25] a moving bed reactor was designed using strontium bromide as storage. Despite reaching uniform temperatures of the bed, the material suffered from salt agglomeration. In [26] a circular moving bed reactor was realised with a vibrating bed, obtaining an increase of heat and mass transfer and, thanks to the vibration of the bed, preventing salt agglomeration.

As part of the Horizon Europe project “ECHO” (Efficient Compact Modular Thermal Energy Storage System) [27], a novel TES system based on a closed-loop thermochemical reactor will be developed. In order to support the design of this novel TES system, anticipating the behaviour of the TCM, preliminary numerical models were developed. Focus of this part of the research was the development of a model for both charge and discharge of the TCM that was able to automatically switch from one to the other, solely based on the boundary conditions. The first results obtained from the simulations are hereafter reported.

2. Numerical model

The first attempts to simulate the behaviour of the hydrated salt were done by only implementing the volume filled with salt, hereafter named TCM bed, using the software COMSOL Multiphysics. With the intention of proceeding in parallel with the ongoing experimental activities in the laboratory, the TCM bed in the numerical model has the same dimensions as the one in the experimental set up. The bed is modelled therefore as a cylinder, with diameter of 0.1 m and height of 0.05 m. To keep the

Figure 1. Geometry implemented in COMSOL Multiphysics along with the conditions imposed: *ht* stands for the “Heat transfer in porous media” module, *br* stands for the “Brinkman Equations” fluid flow module, while *tds* stands for the “Transport of diluted species in porous media” module.

numerical model as simple as possible, the geometry was modelled as 2D-axial symmetric. For the fluid flow across the porous TCM bed the “Brinkman Equations” module was used, for the heat storage and release the “Heat Transfer in porous media” module was used, while for the water vapor adsorption and desorption the “Transport of diluted species in porous media” module was used. In Figure 1 the geometry modelled and the conditions assigned are depicted.

Although the charging and discharging reactions of CaCl_2 occur in multiple steps as in equation (2), at first explorations were carried out by considering only one step, from a complete anhydrous state up to the complete hydration, at 6 molecules of water, and vice versa. The TCM bed is considered as immobile, with a spatially uniform bed porosity. Moreover, at this stage the thermo-physical properties, namely the thermal conductivity and the specific heat, are not function of temperature.

2.1. Mathematical formulation

2.1.1. Reaction kinetics. The reaction kinetics of the salt hydrate, in this case CaCl_2 , depends on three variables, namely temperature T , a time-dependent reaction advancement factor α and pressure p as follows [28]:

$$\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} = k(T) \cdot f(\alpha) \cdot h(p) \quad (3)$$

The reaction advancement factor α reflects the overall conversion degree and is defined between 0, corresponding to a complete dehydration state of the salt, and 1, when the salt is completely hydrated, given by:

$$\alpha(t) = \frac{C(t) - C_0}{C_f - C_0} \quad (4)$$

where C_0 and C_f are the initial and final vapor concentration inside the TCM, respectively. $f(\alpha)$ is function of the advancement factor, that can be expressed as:

$$f(\alpha) = \alpha^c \cdot (1 - \alpha)^d \quad (5)$$

where c and d are two constant parameters. More specifically, during charging c is equal to 1 and d is equal to 0, while during discharging c is equal to 0 and d is equal to 1.

As regards the pressure dependence, the term $h(p)$ can be expressed in case of hydration as:

$$h(p) = 1 - \frac{p_{eq}}{p_v} \quad (6)$$

while during dehydration as:

$$h(p) = \frac{p_v}{p_{eq}} - 1 \quad (7)$$

where p_v and p_{eq} are the partial and the equilibrium pressure of vapor, respectively. With the assumption that mass transfer and chemical reaction occur rapidly enough to keep the process at the prevailing temperature, the equilibrium pressure p_{eq} and temperature T can be correlated by the Clausius-Clapeyron relationship:

$$\ln(c) = -\frac{\Delta H}{R \cdot T_{ref}} + \frac{\Delta S}{R} \quad (8)$$

where p_{ref} is the reference pressure [Pa], ΔH is the reaction enthalpy [J/mol], T_{ref} is the reference temperature [K], ΔS is the reaction entropy [J/(mol·K)].

2.1.2. Mass conservation. With the assumption that no mass is exchanged between the TCM bed and the surrounding environment, the density of the hydrated salt decreases throughout the charging process while the density of the dehydrated salts and water vapor increase. The mass transfer equation for the water vapor can be defined as:

$$\varepsilon \frac{\partial \rho_v}{\partial t} = S_w - \nabla(\rho_v \vec{u}) + D_g \Delta \rho_v \quad (9)$$

where ε is the porosity of the salt bed, D_g is the water vapor diffusion coefficient in the porous bed while S_w is the mass source, which can be expressed as follows:

$$S_w = z \rho_s \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} \frac{M_v}{M_s} \quad (10)$$

where z is the stoichiometric number of the reaction and $\frac{M_v}{M_s}$ is the ratio between the molecular mass of vapor and that of the salt.

2.1.3. Energy conservation. The energy balance in the salt bed can be defined as:

$$(1 - \varepsilon) \rho_s c_s \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \nabla(\lambda_s \nabla T) - \rho_v c_v \vec{u} \nabla T + \dot{q} \quad (11)$$

where ρ_s is the density of the salt, c_s and c_v are the specific heat of the salt and of the water vapor, respectively, λ_s is the salt thermal conductivity and \dot{q} is the energy source term that can be expressed as:

$$\dot{q} = \pm z \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} \frac{\rho_s}{M_s} \Delta H \quad (12)$$

In case of hydration the sign is positive, hence the reaction is exothermic, while during dehydration, which is endothermic, the sign is negative.

2.2. Charging and discharging conditions

In order for the model to switch autonomously from charge to discharge of the TCM, it was necessary to define under which conditions the TCM was actually being charged rather than discharged. The factors affecting the reaction of the material are the temperature and the vapor content of the air passing through it.

The charging of the TCM, hence its dehydration, can be done by working on the air passing through it: (i) increasing the temperature, (ii) decreasing the vapor content, (iii) both of the above-mentioned. On the contrary, the discharging of the TCM can be done: (i) decreasing the temperature of the air passing through, (ii) increasing the vapor content, (iii) both decreasing the temperature and increasing the vapor content. In Figure 2 the light blue area indicates that the material at those conditions in terms of temperature and vapor pressure is hydrated, while the pink one indicates that the TCM is dehydrated. The darker areas graphically highlight the aforementioned conditions for charging (a) and discharging (b).

Figure 2. Darker rectangular areas depicting the TCM charging (a) and discharging (b) conditions.

The conditions above identified are summarised in Table 1, as assigned to the model.

Table 1. Temperature and vapor pressure conditions set in the numerical model

	$T_{inlet} > T^*$	$T_{inlet} < T^*$	$T_{inlet} = T^*$
$C_{inlet} > C^*$	-	hydration	hydration
$C_{inlet} < C^*$	dehydration	-	dehydration
$C_{inlet} = C^*$	dehydration	hydration	-

T_{inlet} : temperature of inlet air passing through the TCM

C_{inlet} : Vapor concentration of inlet air passing through the TCM

T^* : instantaneous TCM temperature

C^* : instantaneous vapor concentration

3. Results

At first simulations were carried out to verify whether the model was able to switch between charge and discharge solely based on the boundary conditions. However, to give more consistency to the implemented model, the results were compared to the data acquired during the experimental tests carried out in lab. As previously anticipated, the simplification of considering both hydration and dehydration as a single step was adopted, hence the comparison with experimental data is purely qualitative. It should also be pointed out that for this comparison the properties of the TCM have been slightly adjusted so

that the multiple reactions could be merged into a single one. The key parameters assigned to the model are reported in Table 2.

For the comparison, experimental data shown in Figure 3 were used. The test consisted of an initial hydration of the TCM, followed by a partial dehydration and then a hydration phase again. During the hydration phases, a humidifier was used to increase the absolute humidity of the air passing through the TCM. Throughout the entire test ambient air was also constantly heated by means of an electrical heater before passing through the TCM bed. However, during the hydration phases a decrease in the inlet temperature is visible, which was due to evaporative cooling.

Table 2. Key parameters assigned to the model

Parameters	Description	Value	Unit
M_v	Molecular mass of water vapor	18.02	g/mol
M_s	Molecular mass of CaCl_2	110.99	g/mol
ρ_s	Density of CaCl_2	280*	kg/m^3
λ_s	Thermal conductivity of CaCl_2	0.6	$\text{W}/(\text{m}\cdot\text{K})$
c_s	Specific heat of CaCl_2	800	$\text{J}/(\text{kg}\cdot\text{K})$
D_g	Gas diffusion coefficient	$1.685 \cdot 10^{-6}$	m^2/s
ΔH	Reaction enthalpy	65	kJ/mol
ΔS	Reaction entropy	170	$\text{J}/(\text{mol}\cdot\text{K})$
R	Ideal gas constant	8.314	$\text{J}/(\text{mol}\cdot\text{K})$
u	inlet air velocity	0.3	m/s
ϵ	TCM bed porosity	0.8	-
z	stoichiometric number	6	-

* at this stage the vermiculite was not considered, hence the density was adjusted so that the amount of reacting salt was the same as the experimental tests

Figure 3. Boundary conditions in terms temperature and absolute humidity of the inlet air through the TCM.

The results obtained in terms of reaction advancement factor, α , and reaction rate, $\partial\alpha/\partial t$, are reported in Figure 4. Starting from a complete dehydration of the TCM, the first hydration phase between 0.5 h and 1.5 h brought the reaction at about 60%, which means that the material absorbed about 60% of the total amount of water that could be absorbed. As regards the reaction rate, the first peak can be ascribed to the drastic increase in the absolute humidity of the inlet air, which then remained more regular between 20 $\text{g}_v/\text{kg}_{\text{as}}$ and 30 $\text{g}_v/\text{kg}_{\text{as}}$. During the second phase, the humidifier was turned off but the electrical heater was kept constant, hence the dehydration reaction is slightly visible due to the low inlet air temperature, at about 40°C-45°C. The reaction advancement factor barely decreased and also

the reaction rate was close to 0 s^{-1} . During the third and last phase, the humidifier was turned on again and the TCM continued to hydrate. Starting from a reaction advancement factor close to 0.6, this last phase brought the reaction at almost 0.8, thus the reaction was not complete yet. As before, the peak that can be observed at the beginning of the second hydration phase can be ascribed to the drastic increase in the absolute humidity of the inlet air.

The comparison in terms of temperature was carried out at this stage by comparing the temperature monitored close to the middle of the TCM bed with the simulated one in the same position. It was decided not to compare the experimental and the simulated outlet temperatures because the sensor in the experimental set up was not placed close to the TCM bed. From this comparison, depicted in Figure 5a, it emerges that the experimental and simulated trends are similar, but there are consistent differences, even more than 5 K. It is worth reiterating that at this stage of the research it was decided to proceed by simplifying the various reaction steps, and adopting a single value for the reaction enthalpy and reaction entropy inevitably leads to deviations of the simulated data from the experimental ones.

Figure 4. Reaction advancement factor (α) and reaction rate ($\partial\alpha/\partial t$) obtained from the simulation.

Figure 5. (a) Experimental and simulated temperatures in the middle of the TCM bed (b) Experimental and simulated mass variation of the TCM.

The comparison between experimental and simulated mass variation of the TCM is reported in Figure 5b. The trend of the two curves is quite similar, with the most visible difference during the dehydration phase, and at the end of three hours the experimental mass variation is of 41.2 g while the simulated one is 38.9 g, with a difference therefore of 2.3 g.

Based on these results, despite the simplification and the merging of the different reaction steps into a single one, it can be concluded that the conditions set allow the model to automatically switch from charge to discharge and vice versa. Further efforts will be focused on the implementation of the different reaction steps as reported in equation (2). Consequently, more extensive explorations will be carried out regarding the behaviour of the TCM and in order to establish relationships between charging and discharging times.

4. Conclusions

As part of the Horizon Europe project “ECHO”, a preliminary numerical model was realized using COMSOL Multiphysics in order to support the design of a novel closed loop thermochemical reactor. At this stage the focus of the research was the implementation of a model for both charging (dehydration) and discharging (hydration) of the TCM. The first results obtained from the simulations confirmed the model was able to automatically switch from charging to discharging and vice versa, solely based on the boundary conditions. To give more consistency to the results, a comparison between experimental and simulated data was carried out.

Despite the simplifications adopted at this stage, the trends of the experimental and numerical curves are quite similar and, in particular, the simulated TCM mass variation deviates by only 2.3 g from the experimental one. Further efforts will be devoted on the implementation of the different hydration and dehydration steps, which will then be accurately validated against experimental data.

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